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THE TEACHING OF ORAL PRODUCTION IN THE FFL CLASSROOM: LINGUISTIC AND PSYCHOLOGICAL DIFFICULTIES

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Abstract: Nowadays, oral production—which is essential to the teaching and learning process—is given more attention in foreign language instruction. According to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages, oral expression, also known as oral production, is a competence that students must progressively master. It entails using FFL to express themselves in a wide range of contexts. In addition to analyzing the resources used to teach oral production and the best activities for enhancing language proficiency in FFL classrooms, this article clarifies the concept of oral production and its role in FFL learning. To speak French well and express oneself orally and correctly, one must master the language and possess self-confidence. The dream of every foreign language learner is to express oneself orally with ease and spontaneity, thereby achieving perfect mastery of the language.

The major obstacles encountered by learners in oral expression are both psychological and linguistic. It should be noted that the lack of daily oral practice in the French language, insufficient vocabulary and language skills, and poor pronunciation are the primary linguistic problems faced by learners. This does not prevent them from experiencing certain difficulties related to their psychological state, such as the stress of speaking, fear of making mistakes, and a general feeling of discomfort.

Key words: Linguistic elements, grammatical structures, nasal sounds, French as a Foreign Language (FFL), linguistic and communication problems, pronunciation and intonation, morphology and syntax, vocabulary.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda og'zaki nutq o'qitish va o'rganish jarayonining muhim tarkibiy qismi sifatida xorijiy til ta'limida tobora ko'proq e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Yevropa tillari umumiy tavsiyanomalariga ko'ra, og'zaki ifoda (yoki og'zaki nutq) bu – o'quvchilar bosqichma-bosqich egallashi lozim bo'lgan kompetensiyadir. Bu esa FFL (frantsuz tili xorijiy til sifatida) orqali turli holatlarda o'zini erkin ifoda eta olishni anglatadi.

Ushbu maqolada FFL darslarida og'zaki nutqni rivojlantirishda qo'llaniladigan resurslar, eng samarali faoliyat turlari ham tahlil qilinadi, shuningdek, og'zaki nutq tushunchasi va uning FFL o'rganishdagi o'rni yoritiladi. Frantsuz tilida ravon va to'g'ri gapira olish uchun tilni mukammal o'zlashtirish va o'ziga bo'lgan ishonch zarur. Har qanday til o'rganuvchining orzusi – erkin va tabiiy tarzda gapira olish orqali tilni mukammal egallashdir.

Talabalar og'zaki ifoda jarayonida asosan psixologik va lingvistik qiyinchiliklarga duch keladilar. Xususan, frantsuz tilining kundalik og'zaki amaliyoti yetishmasligi, so'z boyligi va til ko'nikmalari pastligi, noto'g'ri talaffuz asosiy lingvistik muammolar hisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari, ular psixologik holat bilan bog'liq muammolarni ham boshdan kechiradilar: gapirishdagi qo'rquv, xatoga yo'l qo'yishdan uyalish, o'zini noqulay his qilish kabi holatlar bunga misoldir.

Kalit so'zlar: Lingvistik elementlar, grammatik tuzilmalar, burun tovushlari, xorijiy til sifatida frantsuz tili (FFL), til va kommunikativ muammolar, talaffuz va intonatsiya, morfologiya va sintaksis, so'z boyligi.

Аннотация: В настоящее время устная речь, являющаяся важным элементом учебного процесса, привлекает всё больше внимания в преподавании иностранных языков. Согласно Общей европейской системе оценивания владения иностранным языком, устная речь, также известная как устное высказывание, является компетенцией, которую учащиеся должны постепенно осваивать. Это предполагает использование французского как иностранного языка (FFL) для самовыражения в самых различных ситуациях. В данной статье рассматриваются не только ресурсы, используемые для обучения устной речи, и наиболее эффективные виды деятельности для повышения языковой компетенции в классах FFL, но и проясняется само понятие устной речи и её роль в процессе изучения французского языка. Чтобы хорошо говорить по-французски и правильно выражать свои мысли устно, необходимо овладеть языком и обладать уверенностью в себе.

Мечта каждого изучающего иностранный язык – свободно и спонтанно выражать свои мысли, тем самым достигнув высокого уровня владения языком. Основные трудности, с которыми сталкиваются учащиеся при устном высказывании, носят как психологический, так и лингвистический характер. Следует отметить, что отсутствие ежедневной устной практики французского языка, недостаточный словарный запас и языковые навыки, а также плохое произношение являются главными лингвистическими проблемами. Кроме того, учащиеся испытывают и психологические затруднения: страх говорить, боязнь ошибиться и чувство дискомфорта.

Ключевые слова: Языковые элементы, грамматические структуры, носовые звуки, французский как иностранный язык (FFL), лингвистические и коммуникативные проблемы, произношение и интонация, морфология и синтаксис, словарный запас.

INTRODUCTION

Foreign language teaching, particularly French as a Foreign Language (FFL), has evolved to meet new objectives and address the changing needs of learners. In general, a new language is learned in order to communicate. The teaching of oral expression has long been a subject of pedagogical and linguistic concern among teachers of FFL. In recent years, oral production has become a top priority in language education. Significant research has been conducted to better understand how oral communication functions, providing deeper insights into teaching practices through the analysis of verbal interactions in language classrooms.

Martinez confirms that oral language holds an important place in modern methodologies and often constitutes the starting point for learning (Martinez, 2014, pp. 92–93). Today, foreign language instruction places greater emphasis on oral production, which lies at the heart of the learning process and has become a central focus of research, particularly with the advent of new techniques for accessing information and using modern communication tools in teaching. In this context, “teaching” means “...to equip the learner with language skills, a concept that combines linguistic and communicative competence” (Galisson, 2002, p. 30).

FFL instruction aims to guide learners toward acquiring the four foundational language skills: listening comprehension, reading comprehension, speaking, and writing. In language education, speaking is described as “the area of language teaching that includes the teaching of the specificity of spoken language and its acquisition through listening and production activities, ideally using authentic audio texts” (Robert, 2008, p. 156).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Oral expression, renamed oral production in accordance with the texts of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), is a skill that learners must gradually acquire in the process of teaching and learning a foreign language. It consists of expressing oneself in a wide variety of situations in French as a Foreign Language (FFL). It is an interactive relationship between a sender and a receiver, which also requires the ability to understand the other.

According to Perrenoud, oral practice can only be formative if it corresponds to a genuine need to express oneself or to understand. In other words, oral pedagogy requires the creation of authentic communication situations, with real challenges between the speakers (Perrenoud, 1988, p. 20).

Oral production currently holds an important place in French didactic research and constitutes a fundamental objective of foreign language teaching. Oral communication is a highly effective means of classroom interaction, enabling learners to acquire language skills when teachers give their students opportunities to speak and express their thoughts in order to develop their communicative competence. Oral communication is considered a tool for interaction in real-life situations; it allows learners to express ideas, verbalize their thoughts, reflect, present and defend their viewpoints, share their beliefs, and finally, reformulate in their own words what they have theoretically understood. By considering oral communication as a learning tool, learners are empowered to express themselves and thereby reconstruct their understanding of the world around them.

It is important to highlight another distinction: the fact that oral communication is sometimes a means of learning and teaching, and sometimes a goal in itself. In foreign language education, oral communication has often held an essential role in the teaching and learning process, both as a subject of instruction and a means

of instruction. Oral production should thus be considered a practical instrument for communication in real-life contexts.

Oral production fulfills a key objective in teaching French as a foreign language. Throughout their learning journey, learners must enrich their knowledge, skills, and competencies so that they can enhance their oral expression by gradually developing it at the linguistic, referential, discursive, and sociocultural levels. Thus, oral expression is both an object and a tool of learning, playing a very important role in language mastery.

Plane explains that "...oral communication can be used as a learning tool, insofar as it becomes a way to clarify and develop the learner's thinking. As a learning object, oral communication is central to the learning activity. Indeed, the term 'oral' is used to designate both pedagogical methods, a tool for learning, and a particularly complex learning object" (Plane, 2015, p. 13).

FFL learners are exposed to spoken language from the very beginning of their studies and aim to be able to communicate orally and acquire both oral expression and comprehension skills as early as possible. The goal of oral production is to help learners communicate in diverse communicative contexts, producing utterances while respecting pronunciation, articulation, intonation, vocabulary, and grammatical structures, as well as employing non-verbal cues (gestures, facial expressions, eye contact, etc.). Teaching oral production helps learners enhance and develop their language skills. What learners need is the ability to communicate in French, to understand its linguistic and pragmatic rules, and to adapt these appropriately to various communicative situations. For foreign language teaching, what is truly important is the development of oral production and familiarity with various oral language practices. Enhancing oral expression to allow learners to communicate as naturally and authentically as possible remains the primary objective of any oral learning approach.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Improving oral expression by enabling learners to communicate in the most natural and authentic way possible remains the primary objective of any oral learning. Regarding the identification of learners' gaps in academic learning, students have difficulty speaking French correctly. They struggle to pronounce words correctly and formulate sentences accurately. They also struggle to find vocabulary words when speaking French. Speaking, especially in a foreign language, is a challenge for some learners.

Students find it difficult to express themselves in French as a foreign language in classes and in various situations where the use of the language is necessary. The majority of learners neither dare to speak nor express themselves orally, nor can they interpret what they think in order to be understood in the various situations they encounter. In academic learning, we have noticed that learners express themselves in a foreign language only on very rare occasions, despite having prior knowledge of all the rules of the French language. To develop automatic reflexes—that is, to communicate effortlessly and correctly—one must become aware of the linguistic elements involved and take the time to practice the language using the correct basic structures.

Speaking a language is more than just knowing a few words; it's also about learning more about the norms that govern the arrangement of sentences. The linguistic component covers the purely technical knowledge of a language. It includes pronunciation, morphology, vocabulary, grammar, syntax, and more. It is in the linguistic component that learners strengthen their four skills: oral expression, written expression, oral comprehension, and written comprehension. Listening comprehension is the core of communication and one of the most important avenues for language acquisition.

Teachers can use multiple teaching aids during class time to improve oral expression, taking into account learners' needs. Thanks to the various supports offered by audiovisual and computer tools, oral comprehension activities are enriched. Audiovisual materials remain a source of language learning because they reproduce real-life comprehension situations. The content of audio materials used in language classes must be thematically linked to the curriculum's teaching units. Simply listening without clear instructions or objectives is not very productive. Audio materials downloaded from the internet lead learners to make judgments about what they hear and decode sounds, which enables them to produce. Video is an extremely valuable medium because it enhances the pleasure of listening to and understanding a foreign language.

For example, the websites [<http://www.francaisfacile.com>] and [<https://www.francaisavec pierre.com>] offer a series of online courses and downloadable interactive video recordings with exercises that aid comprehension. The use of audiovisual materials can help enrich learners' language skills. The document used must be accessible, given its content, length, and topic, and compatible with the students' language level.

Audiovisual aids enable and encourage activities that are impossible to achieve in a traditional classroom and reinforce the teaching/learning process of oral production. To better assimilate words, sounds, pronunciation, and sentence structures, students should be asked to repeat and memorize dialogues by listening to them. Little by little, they will master automatic reflexes for oral production. Students especially have difficulty pronouncing the nasal sounds in French. In French, nasal sounds (nasal vowels) are very important. They are

produced when air exits both the mouth and the nose. This is what differentiates them from oral vowels. There are four main nasal vowels in French:

[ɑ̃] → as in the words: sans, temps, maman

[ɛ̃] → as in: pain, main, matin

[ɔ̃] → as in: nom, long, bon

[œ̃] → as in: un, parfum, commun

These sounds are represented in writing by vowel combinations followed by “n” or “m” such as: an, en, in, un, on. In nasal sounds, the letter “n” or “m” is not pronounced. It only serves to nasalize the vowel. Examples of words with nasal sounds: enfant [ɑ̃], pain [ɛ̃], nom [ɔ̃], un [œ̃].

Nasal sounds are essential for speaking French well. If they are mispronounced, it can completely change the meaning of a word. For example: beau [bo] (pretty) ≠ bon [bɔ̃] (taste), pain [pɛ̃] (food) ≠ peint [pɛ̃] (verb “to paint”). To pronounce them correctly, you need to practice by listening and repeating. French songs and dialogues can help you better recognize them.

Completing tasks allows for the practical application of acquired knowledge and the enrichment of language communication skills. Acquiring oral and written comprehension serves to develop oral and written expression: reading well implies writing well; hearing and listening well, and speaking well implies understanding and expressing oneself well. The combination of listening and practicing spoken French is effective for successfully expressing oneself in a wide variety of situations.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Classroom observations revealed that students appear inhibited in FFL classes and do not always dare to speak up. According to Bialystok, these weaknesses can take many forms: a word, a structure, a sentence, a tense marker, or an idiom (Bialystok, 1990, p. 1). The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) states that learner inhibition strongly influences their performance and task completion. More specifically, it states that a positive self-image and the absence of inhibitions will contribute to successful task execution when the learner has the self-confidence to complete it (CEFR, 2001, p. 122).

The teacher must create a climate that fosters discussion in the classroom so that learners have the opportunity to speak without hesitation. In her comparative study on the role of playful activities as a teaching tool in FFL classrooms, L. Harkou concludes that they have a positive impact on students’ speaking skills (Harkou, 2017, p. 70). According to this study, the main strategies for stimulating learners’ oral expression are: asking questions to get learners to speak or continue speaking, using repetition to encourage them to speak, and finally, asking them to finish a word or sentence started by the teacher (Benamar, 2009, p. 73). However, asking questions was the most effective method for both initiating speech and continuing to speak.

In this sense, the teacher must work on speaking through play. The use of role-playing games develops students’ habit of public speaking. There is a teaching activity: The Psychiatrist Game (Le jeu du psychiatre). This is a popular group game that works very well for an FFL course. The game’s flow is simple: one person is chosen to be the psychiatrist. This person leaves the classroom, and the teacher identifies a common “illness” among the other learners. The psychiatrist returns to the room and begins asking questions of his or her classmates. The learners answer the questions while revealing their “illness.” The psychiatrist continues asking questions until he or she identifies the illness. Here are some examples of “illnesses.” Students can always create more, and learners can also discuss and create their own illness together while the “psychiatrist” is out of the classroom:

- Chacun est convaincu d’être sur une île déserte.
- Le voyage est devenu une obsession pour tous.
- Ils sont persuadés que c’est l’apocalypse.
- Ils sont convaincus qu’ils viennent du futur.
- La couleur rouge obsède tout le monde.

The psychiatrist can ask any questions to try to identify the illness, but here are some examples:

- Qu’as-tu fait aujourd’hui ?
- Quel est ton sport préféré ?
- Quand a eu lieu ton dernier voyage ?
- Avec qui voudrais-tu te rendre au restaurant ?

Another effective activity in the context of oral production is reading aloud in French. Reading is considered one of the best activities in a French as a Foreign Language (FFL) classroom, helping learners acquire a foreign language. It is considered the best way to develop oral production, enrich vocabulary, improve pronunciation, access knowledge, and build understanding. Reading also promotes memorization. It facilitates oral expression and gives all students a voice, especially those who are beginners in French. It’s important to know

that mastering oral production is the result of practice. Reading is one of the most important activities to help students overcome obstacles and difficulties in speaking, due to its many benefits such as enriching vocabulary and improving pronunciation—both of which help develop oral production skills. The key to learning a foreign language is practicing it.

It's important to take into account students' mistakes before they become habitual, but it's crucial not to interrupt learners' oral production. Mistakes should only be corrected at the end of the activity to avoid disrupting communication. E. Charmeux observes: "...teachers intervene in learners' oral expression to finish a sentence or provide an unknown term. On the other hand, continual interruption can demoralize learners, especially when they make mistakes. Being able to speak is not a gift; it is the result of learning" (Charmeux, 1996, p. 19). The teacher, therefore, plays a key role in addressing student errors through their reaction. If a teacher punishes a mistake made by a learner, this can inhibit their ability to express themselves; the learner will think that the teacher expects only correct answers.

Grammatical errors are also common, especially among students learning French. They may make many mistakes in the combination of nouns and adjectives and in the use of tenses in oral speech. For example:

- Ils ont des petits enfant → Ils ont des petits enfants.
- Hier, nous sommes au cinéma pour voir un film intéressant → Hier, nous avons été au cinéma pour voir un film intéressant.
- À cause des travaux, j'ai très fatigué → À cause des travaux, je suis très fatigué.

A psychological block is a mental state in which a person is unable to perform an action or overcome a difficulty, despite their will and desire to do so. Psychological blocks can lead to a loss of self-confidence, feelings of inferiority, or worthlessness. It is possible to overcome them by becoming aware of their existence and working to transform them. Emotions affect our learning, motivation, behavior, and communication with others. To express yourself well in French, it is essential to think carefully before speaking. Most of the time, people who are afraid to express themselves in a foreign language simply fear the judgment of their interlocutor.

The inhibition of a learner's ability to express themselves in French is often linked to stress. Fear of judgment and failure can prevent the speaker from expressing themselves. The fear of being ridiculed, judged by others, or misunderstood can create inhibition and prevent them from engaging in a conversation in a foreign language. Overcoming one's fear of speaking a foreign language requires accepting that they will make mistakes. One of the main reasons that prevent a person from expressing themselves effectively orally is shyness. To overcome psychological difficulties, it is essential to practice speaking by listening to French songs and reading the lyrics. Songs are a tool—almost a pretext—for discovering French culture, history, and values. The teacher can ask students to invent gestures to accompany the intonation and rhythm in the most theatrical way possible to raise their awareness. It should be noted that gestures are not used to accompany the meaning of words or sentences.

CONCLUSION

Finally, it should be noted that while learning to express oneself in a foreign language (French) can be challenging, students must strive to become proficient in spoken language, and teachers must assist them in developing oral communication skills. Many learners wish to improve their French but are hindered by conventional teaching methods (vocabulary lists, grammar rules, etc.). In foreign language teaching and learning, the emotional aspect is rarely emphasized in academic literature. However, it can be a crucial element for successful learning.

In FFL classrooms, teachers should provide authentic and motivating activities. What learners truly need is the ability to communicate in a foreign language, understand its linguistic and usage rules, and adapt them to different communication contexts. Teachers must create opportunities for student participation and encourage them to speak French, even if they make mistakes. Learners appreciate when teachers correct errors constructively rather than embarrass them.

To speak French fluently and express oneself accurately, one must master the language and possess self-confidence. To overcome difficulties, teachers increasingly use strategies such as designing diverse activities that promote speaking and immerse students in oral communication situations. Most teachers find it necessary to provide more opportunities for students to speak and express themselves in class.

The primary cause of students' weak oral expression skills appears to be a significant lack of practice and limited authentic exposure to the French language. Practicing oral skills fosters fluency, resulting in spontaneous and accurate speech. Utilizing playful activities has proven to be an effective approach to improving oral production. For many French language teachers, teaching oral production remains a vague or underdeveloped practice in the classroom. Learning a foreign language involves more than memorizing vocabulary and grammar rules; it also includes embracing new ways of thinking, exploring different cultures, and engaging in a

rich intellectual experience. Therefore, it is preferable to involve learners in oral activities that stimulate critical thinking, enrich their knowledge, and simultaneously enhance their communicative and discourse competence.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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